

Implications of Extending the Village Head's Working Period on The Effectiveness of Village Government

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Keywords : <i>Extending, Working Period, Village Government.</i></p> <p>Submitted: 28-12-2023</p> <p>Last revised: 30-04-2024</p> <p>Accepted: 15-05-2024</p> <p>Published: 28-06-2024</p>	<p>This research aims to determine the implications of extending the Chief of Village's time of office on the effectiveness of village government administration and what factors can influence the effectiveness of village government administration. This type of research is normative juridical research which seeks to solve problems by studying legal norms using Law in books or studies from relevant library materials. The results of this research show that firstly, extending the term of office of the Chief Village is completely irrelevant to the urgency of the need to improve Village government at this time so that it has no implications for the effectiveness of village government administration and continuity of development, the argument for extending the term of office is more like the subjective reasons of the Village Heads and tends to have a political nuance. Second, the fundamental factors that must be synchronized are the Village Head's leadership, partnership and collaboration with external parties and more substantial community participation and involvement. If these factors can be combined optimally then the effectiveness of village government administration will be created regardless of how long a village head has led.</p>

1. Introduction

The Indonesian government system that implements decentralization of power provides conditions for the division of power to regional governments which are defined as the handover of government affairs by the central government, to autonomous regions based on the principle of autonomy. Each region certainly has different problems. Therefore, in the administration of government and the

implementation of regional development, a system is needed in accordance with their respective problems.

Decentralization can also be interpreted as the relationship between local government and central government with the aim of respecting and recognizing the presence of people who are in the local scope in order to increase community identity and initiative to realize the widest autonomy. In the implementation of the decentralization system, the government divides government entities into central government and regional government, which then local governments are again divided into Provincial Governments, Regency / City Governments and Village Governments as the smallest unit of government in Indonesia.

Article 18B paragraph 2 of the 1945 Constitution which is the constitutional basis of village government has clearly outlined that the existence of the village as a legal community unit gives a deep understanding that village institutions are not only administrative entities but also legal entities that must be respected, privileged, preserved and protected in the government system in Indonesia.¹ The village is a territorial law community unit that has the right to regulate and take care of the interests of the local community according to its own initiative in accordance with the aspirations of the community. Therefore, the Village Government carries out three main areas, namely village government, development and community. This business requires collaboration between the leadership of a Village Head and the participation of the people or villagers to be carried out properly.²

Meanwhile, in the general provisions of Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages (hereinafter referred to as the Village Law), village government is defined as the implementation of government affairs and the interests of local communities in the government system of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.³ This regulation gives us an idea that village government is not only a unity of customary law communities but also as the lowest government hierarchy in the Republic of Indonesia. Village governance is becoming increasingly important not only because it is formally part of the Indonesian government system but also because it is substantially a government structure that is directly in contact with the lowest layers of society which is expected to spearhead efforts to create community welfare and poverty alleviation in Indonesia, considering that there are still many poor people in rural areas.

As a logical consequence of the importance of village governance, the role of the Village Head is believed by the community as a key force that can drive village government that is able to build a new culture that is in accordance with the expectations of change, which means that with the leadership capacity possessed by a Village Head will be able to organize effective government to create development and services to the community in the village at its mouth It is hoped that it will create people's welfare and reduce poverty in Indonesia.

¹ Yusnani hazjimzoem, Legal Dynamics of Village Government (Fiat Justitia Journal of Legal Studies Vol.8 No.3, 2018)

² Ni'matul Huda, Village Government Law in the Indonesian Constitution from Independence to Reform (Malang: Setara Press, 2015), 20

³ See Article 1 paragraph (2) Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages

However, in today's dynamics, the term of office of the Village Head is often a controversial discussion, many parties hope that the term of office of the Village Head is increased to more than 6 (six) years but not a few also argue that the current term of office is quite ideal and indeed there is a need for restrictions on power to remain in the corridors of democracy and constitutional principles of the term of office of a political official based on theory and system constitution in Indonesia.

The actions of Village Heads throughout Indonesia some time ago which were expressed in the form of demonstrations in front of the Indonesian Parliament building Senayan Jakarta to voice several demands where one of them was related to the extension of the term of office of Village Heads was finally responded by the House of Representatives of the Republic of Indonesia and the Government by making a second amendment to the Village Law, where several articles were revised and related to the term of office of Village Heads regulated in Article 39 of Law Number 3 of 2024 concerning Amendments secondly on Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages. In this article, it is stipulated that the Village Head holds office for 8 (eight) years and can serve 2 (two) consecutive or non-consecutive terms.

The revision of this regulation will certainly have implications for several aspects of the current village government system, the management and leadership strategy of the Village Head must also change according to the length of the 8-year term of office. Conflict management and procedures for overcoming boredom in leading the village must also be the attention of the current Village Head.

But the next question is whether the duration of tenure is indeed a solution in the implementation of good village governance? As if the success of a Village Head in leading a Village is largely determined by the length or duration of his tenure, or whether the complexity of governance issues in the Village requires other factors in an effort to realize the ideals of village government that is able to create the welfare and independence of the community.

Based on the background and rationale mentioned above, the author will conduct a research entitled Implications of Extending the Term of Office of Village Heads on the Effectiveness of Village Governance.

The formulation of the problem that will be the focus of discussion in this study Is the extension of the term of office of the Village Head able to create effective village governance? What are the factors that affect the effective administration of governance in the village?

2. Method

In writing studies, normative juridical research methods are used, namely legal research through efforts to find solutions to problems through reviewing legal norms using Law in books or studies from literature materials. Meanwhile, the author uses a statutory approach or statue approach that

examines various regulations related to the legal issue of extending the term of office of the village head.

The type of legal material that the author uses is in the form of primary legal material in the form of legislation and secondary legal material such as publications about law or legal literature related to the topic of this paper.

This paper presents the lens and direction of the constitutional concept of the plan to extend the term of office of the village head, analyzes the ideal concept of good village governance and looks at other factors that support the success of the Village Head's leadership in organizing village government in accordance with the *tupoksi* and authority possessed.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Dynamics Chief Of Village's Term in Office Regulation in Indonesia

The state of Indonesia is a state of law. as stipulated in Article 1 paragraph (3) of the 1945 Constitution. The head of state government, regional head and head of village government legally in exercising power must obey and comply with the state constitution. Based on the country's constitution as further stipulated in the laws and regulations under it already regulate the term of office of heads of state, regional heads, MPR, DPR, DPD, DPRD and other government officials in Indonesia.

The tenure regulations regarding cadets of the Old Order, New Order and Reformation are regulated in five laws and regulations. These laws and regulations are Law No.19 of 1965 concerning Desapraja (Law of Desapraja), Law No.5 of 1979 concerning Village Government (Law of Pempdes), Law No.22 of 1999 concerning Local Government (Law of Local Government of 1999), Law No.32 of 2004 concerning Local Government (Law of Local Government 2004), and Law No.6 of 2014 (Law of Village) which was subsequently last amended and regulated in Law Number 3 of 2024 (Law of Village Second Amendment).

First, the regulation in Article 9 paragraph (2) of the Desapraja Law regulates the term of office of the Village Head for a maximum of 8 (eight) years, without being followed by the Article whether or not he can be re-elected.⁴ Second, Article 7 of the Local Government Law stipulates that the term of office of the Village Head is 8 (eight) years and can be reappointed for one term.⁵

Third, the regulation in the 1999 Local Government Law, Article 96 which regulates the term of office of the Village Head for a maximum of ten years or two terms of office starting from the date stipulated.⁶ This provision is equipped with an explanatory part of Article 96 which states that the Regency can determine the term of office of the Village Head in accordance with the local socio-culture. That is, the exception to the limited tenure is possible insofar as there are provisions governing the local culture, in this case indigenous villages.⁷

⁴ See Article 9 Paragraph (2) Law Number 19 of 1965 concerning Villages.

⁵ See Article 7 of Law Number 5 of 1979 concerning Village Government.

⁶ See Article 96 of Law Number 22 of 1999 concerning Regional Government

⁷ Widya Rahadiyanti, "Juridical Analysis of the Constitutional Court's Considerations in Limiting the Period of Office of Village Heads (Case Study: Decision of the Indonesian Constitutional Court Number 42/PUU-XIX/2021)" (National University, 2022), 3-4.

Fourth, the regulation of the term of office of village heads in the 2004 Local Government Law. Article 204 stipulates that the term of office of the village head is six years and can be re-elected only for one subsequent term.⁸ Similar to the 1999 Local Government Law, the Explanation of this Article excludes restrictions on the term of office of Kades for the unity of indigenous peoples whose existence is still alive and recognized as stipulated by local regulations.⁹

Fifth, the regulation of the term of office of the village head in the Village Law. Article 39 paragraph (1) of the Village Law limits the term of office of the Village Head to only 6 (six) years and Article 39 paragraph (2) stipulates that the Village Head as referred to in paragraph (1) can serve a maximum of three consecutive or non-consecutive terms.¹⁰ In its latest development, the current term of office of the Village Head as stipulated in the Village Law is amended and regulated in Article 39 of the Second Amendment Village Law which stipulates that the term of office of the Village Head is for 8 (eight) years and can serve a maximum of 2 (two) consecutive or non-consecutive terms.¹¹

Seeing the comparison of laws and regulations governing the term of office of village heads in the discussion above, it is increasingly emphasized that basically the rules related to the term of office of village heads are Open Legal Policy or open legal policies from the government and the framers of laws that are political, even though from the other side in democratic principles there is a limitation of power.

The dynamics of changes in arrangements regarding the term of office of the Village Head are highly dependent on the philosophical, juridical and sociological conditions as well as legal politics that affect at the time the provision is made. If at any time the framer of the law is of the opinion that by taking into account the development of the community there will be a need to limit the term of office of the village head, including by determining the periodization of the term of office which may be different from the previous provisions.¹²

3.2 Limitation Chief of Village Term Of Office in Indonesia

Democracy and the rule of law are two conceptions of power mechanisms in running the wheels of state government. The two conceptions are interrelated with each other inseparable, because on the one hand democracy provides the foundation and mechanism of power based on the principle of equality and equality of human beings, on the other hand the state of law provides a benchmark that those who govern in a state are not humans, but laws.¹³

Likewise, related to the mechanism of determining the power of village government cannot be separated from the state system of law and democracy, where political power in the context of preparing legal instruments as a tool to exercise power, including preparing the formulation of norms that regulate the term of office of village heads is inseparable from the democratic system in the state

⁸ See Article 204 of Law Number 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government

⁹ Widya Rahadiyanti, *Op.Cit*

¹⁰ See Article 39 of Law Number 6 of 2014

¹¹ See Article 39 of Law Number 3 of 2024 concerning the Second Amendment to Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages.

¹² Constitutional Court Judge Enny Nurbaningsih's legal considerations in Constitutional Court Decision No.15/PUU-XXI.2023

¹³ Muntoha, M. (2009). Democracy and the Rule of Law. *Ius Quia Iustum Law Journal*, 16(3), 379–395.

of law. Although in its position the village has the lowest administrative power of the government in the government structure, in general it does not escape the principle of limiting power.

The limitation in question is not only in terms of tenure, but also in terms of periodization of tenure. This is done not only in order to open up opportunities for leadership generation transfer at the village level, but also to prevent the abuse of power (power tends to corrupt) because of too long in power.¹⁴ In simple terms, if we look at the dynamics of laws and regulations regarding villages or village government, since 1965 until now, the regulation of tenure and periodization of the term of office of the Village Head has never been absent from the limitation of power. The limitation of power is actually an arrangement in line with the principle of constitutional democracy that seeks realizing the prevention of village government arbitrariness so that it can realize the essence of governance that not only upholds the principle of autonomy, but also democratic principles. This dimension shows how village governments play a very crucial role in realizing the implementation of democracy at the bottom of the State power.

Term limits for village heads are part of the realization of democratic life at the grassroots political level. The Central Government, Regional Government has determined its term of office which is 5 (five) years for one period, the term of office is final and will not be changed to above 5 (five) years, because it is a democratic political decision because basically in a democratic perspective the limitation of power is to provide political opportunities for the entire community to appear in the election of village heads as long as they meet the existing terms and conditions, Because it concerns the rights and interests of the people.

3.3 The Role's Chief Of Village in Village Government

In the general provisions of the Village Law, Village Government is the implementation of government affairs and the interests of local communities in the government system of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. While the Village Government is the Village Head or referred to by other names assisted by village officials as an element of Village Government administration.

The rationale in the arrangement regarding the village is as follows:¹⁵

1. **Diversity**, which means that the term Village can be adjusted to the origin and cultural conditions of the local community. This means that the pattern of governance and implementation of development in the village must respect the value system that applies to the local community but must still pay attention to the shared value system in the life of the nation and state.
2. **Participation**, which means that the administration and development of the village must be able to realize the active role of the community so that the community always has and participates in the development of life together as fellow villagers.
3. **Original Autonomy**, which means that the authority of the village government in regulating and managing the local community is based on the origins and socio-cultural values found in the local community but must be held in the perspective of state government administration that always follows the times.

¹⁴ Jimly Asshiddiqie, Introduction to Constitutional Law (Jakarta: Rajawali Press, 2019), p. 327

¹⁵ Ida Syafriani, The Role of Village Heads in Development, (Wiraraja University E-Journal Vol.3 2019)

4. Democratization, means that the administration and implementation of development in the village must accommodate the aspirations of the community who are articulated and aggregated through the Village Consultative Body and community institutions as partners of village government.
5. Community empowerment, which means the implementation of governance and the implementation of development in the village is aimed at improving the standard of living and welfare of the community through the establishment of policies, programs and activities that are in accordance with the essence of the problem and the priority of community needs.

These are 5 rationales in managing government in the village that must be understood by a Village Head in order to realize the village community as an independent community entity.

Meanwhile, if we look at the regulations and laws and regulations governing the village, we can define the Village Head as someone who has the task of carrying out village government affairs, carrying out village development and empowering the village community who has the authority, including arrangements for community life in accordance with village authority, which if summarized then such as making village regulations, establishing village community institutions, the establishment of village-owned enterprises, and cooperation between villages, development affairs, including community empowerment in the provision of village public facilities and facilities, such as village roads, village bridges, village irrigation, village markets and community affairs which include community empowerment through fostering the socio-cultural life of the community such as health, education and customs.

The authority's Chief of the Village based on the Village Law is:¹⁶

- a. Lead the administration of Village Government;
- b. Appoint and dismiss Village officials;
- c. Holding the power of financial management and Village Assets;
- d. Establish village regulations;
- e. Establish the Village Revenue and Expenditure budget;
- f. Fostering the lives of village communities;
- g. Fostering peace and order in the village community;
- h. Fostering and improving the village economy and integrating it in order to achieve a productive scale economy for the greatest prosperity of the rural community;
- i. Developing Village sources of income;
- j. Propose and accept the transfer of part of state wealth to improve the welfare of rural communities;
- k. Developing the socio-cultural life of the village community;
- l. Utilizing appropriate technology;
- m. Coordinating participatory village development;
- n. Represent the Village inside and outside the court or appoint a legal representative to represent it in accordance with the provisions of laws and regulations; and
- o. Exercise other authority in accordance with provisions of laws and regulations.

In carrying out his duties and authorities, the Chief of Village is also obliged: ¹⁷

¹⁶ See Article 26 paragraph (2) Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages

¹⁷ Article 26 paragraph (4) Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages

- a. Uphold and practice Pancasila, implement the 1945 Constitution, and maintain and maintain the integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia and Bhinneka Tunggal Ika;
- b. Improve the welfare of the village community;
- c. Maintaining the peace and order of the village community;
- d. Obey and enforce laws and regulations;
- e. Carry out a life of democracy and gender justice;
- f. Implement the principles of village governance that are accountable, transparent, professional, effective and efficient, clean, and free from Corruption, Collusion and Nepotism;
- g. Establish cooperation and coordination with all stakeholders in the village;
- h. Organizing good village government administration;
- i. Managing Village finances and assets;
- j. Carry out government affairs that are the authority of the village;
- k. Resolving community disputes in the village;
- l. Developing the economy of the village community;
- m. Fostering and preserving the socio-cultural values of the village community;
- n. Empowering communities and community institutions in the village;
- o. Developing the potential of natural resources and preserving the environment; and
- p. Provide information to the village community.

That is the complexity of the authority and duties that must be carried out by a Village Head who is required to carry out all these duties for the benefit of the community in his village based on the origin and customs of the local community. In carrying out his duties, the Village Head will be assisted by village officials consisting of Village Secretaries, field technical implementers and regional elements whose numbers are adjusted to local needs and socio-cultural conditions.

The role of the village head in village government does play a very strategic role, because the form of services provided to the community can be in direct contact with the community as service users and the Village Head holds full authority over the running of these tasks even though there are village officials who assist in carrying out their duties and authorities. The elected village head is the majority of the people's choice in contesting democratic village head elections. This means that the village head in exercising his power must fight for the rights and interests of the people, not solely ambitious to maintain and extend his term of office.

3.4 Factors Supporting Village Government

National and regional development is an inseparable part of village development activities. Villages are a socioeconomic and political power base that needs serious attention from the government. Development planning has so far made rural communities as objects of development not as subjects of development. The position of villages and rural communities is the basis of the foundation of the life of the nation and the State of Indonesia in realizing the goals of national development, the

government pays the greatest attention to development in rural areas, it is based on the fact that the village is the place where most of the Indonesian people live.¹⁸

The village government as the lowest government in the process of organizing the Government of the Republic of Indonesia is directly related to the daily life of the community. So the position of the village in the implementation of development has a very important meaning. The village as the lowest unit of government is the target of programs from almost all government agencies.¹⁹

In simple terms, we can conclude that the failure of the program at the village level will have an impact on the failure of the government program above it as well. Moreover, one of the main targets of rural development is to reduce poverty and improve a more decent standard of living which is the main vision of national development in the country. Therefore, village development must involve a large part of the population, the results of which can be enjoyed by the entire community.

The current community assumption that to foster awareness of the village community on the importance of development efforts as a means to improve social conditions and in increasing the participation of village people in development depends a lot on the ability of village leaders, especially leaders and leadership of the village government or Village Head, whereas village development to improve and improve the standard of living and social conditions of rural communities will involve three aspects that most determine, namely the Village Government, the private sector, and especially the villagers themselves.

However, in practice, the role and initiative of the Village Head is still very dominant in planning and implementation in village development even though many theories state that awareness and participation of the village community is an important key to the success of village development. While the private sector as an external aspect also determines because the village as the lowest government requires a lot of cooperation with external parties to accelerate faster development and not solely rely on government funds, even though in essence the village head as the leader of the village government is the main actor in carrying out village government leadership and spearheads the implementation and implementation of village and deep development. Raising awareness of the village community to participate in village development.

In the description above, we can see from several factors that can affect the success of village governance will ultimately boil down to the strategic function of the village head so that it can be said that indeed the village head must have strategic leadership abilities that are expected to produce successful leadership.

If we look at the general picture of strategic leadership, that is, the ability of a leader to anticipate, have vision, and maintain flexibility, empowering others to create necessary strategic changes. The existence of a strategic leader is very necessary in a work environment that is prone to difficult issues.²⁰

Furthermore, strategic leadership is a leader's way of strategizing to realize certain goals. The strategy must map out the steps that need to be taken to move from the current state to the desired state. But

¹⁸ Yisriyanto Ismail, Dikson Junus. Village Head Leadership in Carrying Out Community Empowerment Functions. Journal Of Governance Innovation, Vol.1 No.2 September 2019.

¹⁹ *ibid*

²⁰ Nuryetri Biwilfa, Analysis of Leadership Weaknesses and Suggestions as a Leader to be able to carry out their duties effectively. (Director General of Defense Potential) kemhan.go.id.

good leaders should not make strategies based solely on "for now" decisions but should consider long-term development goals.²¹

In addition, here are six other important competencies that a strategic leader must possess:

- a. Anticipatory;
- b. Open mind;
- c. Resourceful;
- d. Make decisions quickly;
- e. Diplomacy skills; and
- f. Not afraid of failure.

In simple terms, we can see that related to the success of a leadership does not depend on the vulnerability of the tenure possessed but rather on the ability of strategic leadership who is able to formulate short-term plans and long-term plans in accordance with the tenure owned, to then make good use of every time they have to work with strategies that are prepared to realize the ideals of development and increase welfare for The entire community led him.

Current village problems are more directed towards a number of problems, ranging from exclusive financial management, meaningless community participation to corruption in various aspects. This results in the development and welfare of rural communities running not optimally including reducing the potential for corruption, collusion and nepotism.

The success of village development cannot be separated from the various supporting factors. The various supporting factors include Village Head Leadership and Community Participation as well as private involvement. Although there are many other factors outside these factors that also influence, such as Village Development Assistance Funds, guidance and support from the top-level Government, various programs both from ministerial and non-ministerial vertical agencies, and or from other existing autonomous agencies, but if they are not supported by good leadership from their Village Head and do not get participation support from the community Concerned, the development of the village will be difficult to realize.

4. Conclusion

Regulations related to the term of office of the Village Head since 1965 until now have never been absent from the laws and regulations. This shows that Indonesia as a state of law and upholding democracy makes the tenure of a public official a special arrangement that must be given legal certainty. The changes in the rules of periodization and tenure of the Village Head are constitutional dynamics because changes in arrangements regarding the term of office of the Village Head are highly dependent on philosophical, juridical and sociological conditions as well as legal politics that affect when the provision is made.

Although currently the extension of the term of office of Village Heads has been authorized by the Government through changes to the Village Law and is a legal thing because it is an open legal policy and does not contradict the country's Constitution, this shows that basically the arguments of Village

²¹ *ibid*

Heads who postulate the extension of the term of office for the effectiveness of village governance and continuity of development are completely irrelevant to the urgency of the need revamping the current Village government.

The argument for extending the term of office of the village head is more like a subjective reason for the village heads and tends to be political, because to determine whether or not the implementation of government in the village is effective there are at least 3 (three) fundamental factors that must be synchronized, namely the Village Head Leadership factor, partnership and cooperation with external parties and more substantial community participation and involvement. If these factors can be mixed optimally, the effectiveness of village governance will be created without having to look at how long a village head leads because it has been adjusted from the beginning to the term of office as outlined in the long-term plan, both the development of rural infrastructure and sustainable empowerment of rural communities.

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